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**Initial assessment of developments and revision of
the scientific challenges - Predicting Near-Earth
Space Dynamics with Vlasiator**

WP1: Plasma Simulations - Codes and Grand Challenges

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Executive Summary

In this deliverable, we provide an update of the development efforts of the Vlasiator simulation code, especially focusing on new achievements within the year 2023. We outline the major areas of code development as part of the Plasma-PEPSC project, and quantify the performance benefit that the simulation has obtained. Since the start of this CoE project was marked with major code restructuring for GPU-enabled simulations and more efficient timestepping, the full computational potential of the new developments has not been realized yet, and will only show up in performance measures after they have been merged into the main development branch.

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1 Introduction

Vlasiator[1], like the other simulation codes in the Plasma-PEPSC centre of excellence, is a kinetic plasma simulation system. As opposed to the other participating codes, its scientific focus area is the simulation of the near-Earth space environment, thus operating at vastly different scales and unique boundary conditions.

2 Revision of the Scientific Challenge

The vision and grand scientific challenges of Vlasiator remain unchanged: With a goal to simulate Earth's entire magnetospheric domain in 3 dimensions using kinetic physics, the target reference case remains identical to the specification in the previous period's deliverable D1.4.

3 Summary of developments

With major development efforts each still residing in their own development branches, the baseline Vlasiator performance in the merged production branch has not been affected as significantly. In the following sections, we provide updates on previously planned and newly envisioned development paths.

3.1 GPU porting

A GPU-compatible port of Vlasiator has been envisioned for several years already, with preliminary work towards directive-based OpenACC porting taking place in 2019 and 2020. A dedicated push towards porting critical functionality of Vlasiator to CUDA and HIP/ROCm has been underway since the beginning of 2021, with much progress during 2023. A scientific publication reporting on progress so far is under preparation and is expected to be submitted to a relevant journal still during 2023.

3.1.1 Vlasov solver porting

In January of 2023, the semi-Lagrangian acceleration solver of Vlasiator had been ported to a CUDA kernel, utilizing unified memory for storing distribution function data. At that time, all velocity space adjustment (adding and deleting blocks), initialization, load balance, and translation took place on CPU only, again facilitated by use of unified memory.

In April 2023, block adjustment was successfully ported to CUDA made possible by in-house developed portable unified memory vector and hash map constructs [2]. In May 2023, the translation solver was ported to CUDA, save for adjustments performed due to remote MPI task contributions. This indicated the first case of the Vlasov solvers operating wholly in device memory. A critical tool in this porting process was the use of unified memory vectors which allowed the correct data to be accessible at all times from both host and device sides.

During the fall of 2023, distribution function initialization, memory buffer allocation, file I/O, checkpointing and restarting, and translation remote contribution use were

improved drastically. Significant improvements were achieved by utilizing and re-using pre-allocated padded memory buffers as much as possible.

Despite transitioning to device-side operations, utilizing unified memory prefetching and multiple streams, GPU performance remains at levels which cannot be applied to global runs. This is partly due to memory slowdowns resulting from prefetching and/or page faulting within the unified memory subsystem. Another contributing factor is that the column construction and block adjustment algorithms, despite having been rewritten to be performed by kernels, are still somewhat sequential in nature. Although they have been somewhat parallelized, they may rely strongly on atomic operations which may cause stalling of the system. Further optimization with the specific goal of tackling these slowdowns is planned.

3.1.2 Unified codebase for CUDA and HIP/ROCm

In June of 2023, the applicability of our CUDA / HIP/ROCm approach was validated, when Vlasiator was successfully ran on LUMI-G with 8 MPI tasks, each with 7 CPU threads equalling 7 GPU streams, with minor adjustments after automatic conversion from CUDA to HIP code. Later during the summer, the codebase was refactored into utilizing compiler directives. In our approach, a single unified codebase, with generalized GPU macros, is re-defined into CUDA or HIP calls by the compiler pre-processor, as requested by user-defined flags.

3.1.3 Field solver

During the summer of 2023, the field solver operations were ported to utilize a lambda-based flexible kernel construction interface. Versions exist both for maintaining dual buffers, one on host and one on device, as well as a unified memory version. The person responsible for this part of the porting has since exited the project, but has made all development branches available to the team. Merging into the general GPU codebase has been postponed until identical performance compared to the CPU codepath (up to numerical precision) can be verified.

Another development which stemmed from the GPU porting is that of dividing Vlasov and field solver tasks to separate sub-communicators within the whole MPI system, providing dedicated tasks for these computational loads. This will result in particular in less ghost communication for the field solver. An initial version of this feature split has been developed with functionality validated, but due to incomplete refactoring of the main simulation loop the subsets of MPI tasks are not yet able to perform these computations in parallel. Optimization of this computation and refactoring of FSgrid decomposition for a smaller number of tasks is planned for spring 2024.

3.1.4 Ionospheric solver

A GPU-based solver for the ionospheric portion of Vlasiator has been created, but still awaits merging into the main codebase. A hindrance is that it was written by a person who has since exited the project, and it utilizes yet another memory management approach. Due to the ionospheric solver taking only a small amount of time of our total compute time, this solver has been deemed a low priority.

3.2 Non-global timestepping (“Time classes”)

It is especially the high contrast of simulated magnetic field strength and plasma density, between the outer simulation solar wind conditions and the inner boundary cells close to Earth, that result in a large spread of length- and timescales inside the domain. Hence, grid resolution and timestep length are limited to the finest required scale throughout the box, unless explicit efforts are taken to alleviate this global requirement.

Implementation of Vlasiator’s adaptive mesh refinement (AMR, see [3]) in the last years has freed the system of this stringent requirement for its spatial resolution, but a global limit on the simulation timestep length had still been in place. Hence, one major Vlasiator development focus throughout the year 2023 has been the decoupling of simulation time step from a globally synchronous stepping to adaptive substepping of cells based on their “time class” (local timestep requirement, quantized to the smallest overall timestep in the simulation).

This new method required a major rework of the grid library’s neighbour handling, as edge cases in time resolution and mesh refinement domain edges conflicted with its philosophy of neighbour finding. As an additional performance benefit, this reduced the number of superfluous neighbor updates and hence overall MPI traffic.

However, these changes are still in their final debugging stages and have not made it into the main development branch, so no impact on the overall code performance is recorded yet.

3.3 Development practices

Shortly after the start of the Plasma-PEPSC project, a continuous integration setup has been taken into use (its initial state had already been documented in deliverable D1.4).

In the interim, the test coverage of this system, and its adoption and reliance by the core development team have expanded, and it had a noticeably positive impact on our development speed.

Nonetheless, as the whole CoE and its partnership with CASTIEL2 has to date not yet been able to secure resources on EuroHPC systems for systematic CI/CD testing at scale, the continuous integration testing currently remains restricted to the computing facilities available locally. Concretely, Github actions are employed, with local runners on the “Carrington” cluster at the University of Helsinki, and the HCA cluster at Barcelona Supercomputing centre, which allows us to automatically test the code on platforms such as ARM64 and RISC-V. The University of Helsinki local clusters do provide CUDA and HIP interfaces for Nvidia hardware, making a GPU branch CI interface also possible, but this has not yet been implemented. Our primary development workflow at Vlasiator’s Github repository directly triggers the CI actions.

4 Revision of Gap analysis

The gap analysis presented in D1.4 still holds, as much of the progress achieved during the course of 2023 has been limited to improving the readiness of GPU functionality and re-writing our grid library to provide better managing of MPI neighbourhood cell lists. Performance evaluation of realistic test cases has not yet been possible in either

branch in their current development state. Hence, neither has been merged into the main development branch so far and their performance benefits have not been quantified. We expect the actual performance benefits to be actualized later during the project.

5 Revision of Roadmap

Identical to the Roadmap outlined in D1.4, the major performance bottleneck of Vlasiator's main loop, caused by load imbalance and resulting in a major percentage of simulation time spend in `MPI_Waitall()` function calls waiting for synchronization from neighboring tasks, continues to be the main driver of Vlasiator development and continues to be at the top of our roadmap.

Other progress in code development has not yet triggered a need to revise our goals or timeline.

Once the aforementioned efforts, GPU solvers and nonhomogeneous timestepping, have been merged during the year 2024, development efforts will continue to focus on load balancing algorithms and their increasingly complex interaction with mesh refinement and timestepping. Compare deliverable D3.1 for an overview of the current state of the art in Vlasiator load balancing processes.

6 Conclusion

Vlasiator code development has started some substantial algorithmic and architectural improvements throughout the year 2023. Primary focus lay on GPU porting of the code, and implementation of nonhomogeneous timestepping. Both development paths have progressed well, but are not yet at a point where a measurable performance impact towards the project goals can be provided. It is expected that they are realized during the year 2024.

Overall, Vlasiator's development practices have evolved into a more structured form, thanks to the experience and knowledge exchange in the ongoing Plasma-PEPSC project.

References

- [1] Minna Palmroth, Urs Ganse, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Markus Battarbee, Lucile Turc, Thiago Brito, Maxime Grandin, Sanni Hoilijoki, Arto Sandroos, and Sebastian von Alfthan. Vlasov methods in space physics and astrophysics. *Living Reviews in Computational Astrophysics*, 4(1):1, August 2018.
- [2] Konstantinos Papadakis, Markus Battarbee, Urs Ganse, Yann Pfau-Kempf, , and Minna Palmroth. Hashinator: A portable hybrid hashmap designed for heterogeneous high performance computing. *Submitted to IEEE Transactions on Parallel and Distributed systems*, 2023.
- [3] Urs Ganse, Tuomas Koskela, Markus Battarbee, Yann Pfau-Kempf, Konstantinos Papadakis, Markku Alho, Maarja Bussov, Giulia Cozzani, Maxime Dubart, Harriet George, Evgeny Gordeev, Maxime Grandin, Konstantinos Horaites, Jonas Suni, Vertti Tarvus, Fasil Tesema Kebede, Lucile Turc, Hongyang Zhou, and Minna Palmroth. Enabling technology for global 3d + 3v hybrid-vlasov simulations of near-earth space. *Physics of Plasmas*, 30(4):042902, April 2023.